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Employees' Workplace Well-Being and Organizational Citizenship Behavior of Private Education in Ilocos Norte, Philippines

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Abstract. The study intended to determine the effect of workplace well-being particularly hedonic and eudemonic well-being on the organizational citizenship behaviour of the employees. To support the theoretical foundation of the study, related literature was reviewed. The respondents of the study were all employees from the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region. The study applied descriptive assessment and correlational research design. To analyse the data, the weighted mean and Pearson r correlation was used. The study found that the workplace well-being of employees and their organizational citizenship behaviour were considered high and it was also found that there is no correlation between the workplace well-being and the organizational citizenship behaviour of the employees. Therefore, the hypothesis of the study, that there is a correlation between workplace well-being and organizational citizenship behaviour is rejected. This finding contributes to a wider discussion on the effect of workplace well-being on organizational citizenship behaviour.

Keywords. workplace well-being, hedonic, eudemonic, autonomy, relatedness, competence

Introduction

Achieving a high-performance organization is a result of many aspects of people management. One important aspect of an organization is its employees. Leading an organization is leading people. The manager needs to understand the effect of his behaviour on the employee and their performance (UNSW, 2015). How the manager leads its people to perform their duties and responsibilities is a crucial element of management. Employees are the most important asset of an organization (Gabcanova, 2011). Though the term "asset" is degrading, management literature has been considered human resources as assets of the organization. Managing human resources means taking care of employees for them to be productive, loyal, and motivated (Skinner, 1981). Skinner (1981) pointed out the decrease in productivity is not caused by any other things such as the absence of strike, wrong strategic direction, lack of government

intervention, not in the public confidence and trust of the society in the business, etc., but it is the poor management of people. Poor management of the workforce can damage the organization and even society indirectly. Poor management does not refer to pay or salary but it is related to how other aspects of the working environment such as a safer workplace, less formal, participation in decision making, good working relationship with employees and management, and fewer overt demands of employees (Skinner, 1981). In other words, management should focus not only on financial rewards but taking care of the workplace well-being of employees.

As a result of the humanistic management approach to management, the focus of management is no longer on rules, procedures, and scientific methods of decision making but focuses on managing people with their values and needs. The centre is a human being and therefore, the aspects to be given attention are not just their salary and benefits but their physical and emotional well-being. In other words, employees must feel safe and happy in the workplace. The recent development indicates that the companies have taken seriously workplace well-being issues and making it their top priority (O'Donnel, 2014). CIPD as cited by Talent Culture (2014) defines employees' well-being as "Creating an environment to promote a state of contentment which allows an employee to flourish and achieve their full potential for the benefit of themselves and their organization." This definition refers to employees' well-being as a workplace environment where people feel happy and contented. This definition is not far different from what ILO (2020) defines as workplace well-being. It defines workplace well-being as "all aspects of working life, from the quality to the safety of the physical environment, the climate at work, and the organization". This definition provides a broad scope of well-being which include physical working environment and psychological environment that may include feelings and working relationship (Skinner, 1981) as Skinner (1981) contended that "employees are looking for more comfort, more relaxation, more freedom from pressures, more benefits and higher pay, not more productivity and loyalty".

Employees' well-being is considered one of the factors that affect the performance of the organization as pointed out above. Its effect may not be limited to organizational performance but even extends beyond the performance which may include the organizational citizenship behaviour of the employees toward the organization. The current research intends to venture into new territory which is the effect of workplace well-being toward the organizational citizenship behaviour of the employees.

The study is divided into five parts. The first part is the introduction that discusses the rationale of the study. The second part is the related literature which presents the theories of the study based on the different related literature and studies. The third part is the research methodology. It presents the methodology of the study that includes the research design, population of the study, the locale of the study, data gathering procedures, research instruments, and statistical treatment of data. The fourth part is the empirical data and analysis which presents the data gathered through research questionnaires and analysis. The fifth is the result and discussion and conclusion.

Literature Review

A literature review is a comprehensive summary of previous researches or ideas presented in the books on the current topic. Thus, it may encompass the books, scholarly research articles, and other sources that are relevant to the discussion of the current investigation (the Bloomsburg University of Pennsylvania, n.d). It presents the theoretical base of the current study and provides a clear picture of the theories of the current study (McCombes, 2020). Thus,

in line with the current study, a related literature review presents the theories of the study which is based on the literature.

Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

The Concept of Workplace Well-Being: Hedonic and Eudemonic

The main question to be raised is: "why is well-being important?" Organizations that are offering higher salaries do not always translate into their workers' well-being. It is the same with high GDP countries. High GDP does not always correlate to the high well-being of their citizens because well-being is subjective (NEF, 2014). This was pointed out by Blanchflower and Oswald (2011) that GDP growth in the United States has not been correlated to subjective well-being. Giving attention to employees' well-being can benefit not only the employees but also benefit the organization. It can release the energy to work smarter and become more creative, loyal, and productive and improve customer satisfaction (NEF, 2014). Thus, workplace well-being cannot be ignored because ignoring it can cause a lot to the organization. It can reduce the output of employees' work, produce conflict, turnover, sickness, sick leave, and many more. Well-being in the workplace issues must be taken as a priority of management. BusinessBalla (2020) emphasized that employees' well-being is a duty of care of employers to the employees. Abun (2018) also contend that it is one of the most important responsibilities of management to care for the organization and employees' well-being. Therefore, understanding the meaning of well-being is important for us to understand the meaning of well-being in the workplace. Merriam-Webster defines well-being as "a state of being happy, healthy or prosperous". This definition is the same as the definition in the Cambridge Dictionary which defines well-being as "a state of being happy and healthy". While LEXICO, the Oxford Dictionary defines well-being as "a state of being comfortable, healthy or happy". Deci and Ryan (2008) as cited by Czerw (2019) consider well-being as a positive state as a result of the experience of emotions and the cognitive assessment of our life. While workplace well-being means the enjoyment that one experiences from the job (Rothausen, 2013). It is the contribution of the job toward the fulfilment of enjoyment. Thus, the workplace well-being that this paper is discussing is the experience of enjoyment in the employment setting. The concept provides us with a better idea about what workplace well-being means. The argument leads us to two important aspects of well-being which are mind and body, physical and psychological. Therefore, workplace well-being means the state of working life which starts from the quality and safety of the working environment up to how the workers feel about their work, their working environment, and the organizational climate as a whole (ILO, 2020). WHO (2012) defines workplace well-being as "a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity". The definitions give us a deeper classification of two types of workplace well-being namely hedonic and eudemonic well-being. On one hand, hedonic workplace well-being refers to a pleasant life such as pleasure, enjoyment, and comfort. On the other hand, workplace eudemonic well-being is related to growth, authenticity, and meaning (Biswas-Diener, et.al. Bartels, et.al. (2019). According to Biswas-Diener, et.al (2009) and Huta and Waterman (2014) workplace well-being can be analyzed from these two dimensions. They argued that the two dimensions can be used to measure well-being in the workplace. Bartels, et.al (2019) lamented that most of the studies on workplace well-being have been focusing only on one dimension of workplace well-being or focusing only hedonic aspect of well-being which is focusing on happiness and an individual's cognitive and affective dimension of his/her life (Diener, 2000).

It has been recognized that there is no comprehensive definition of workplace well-being and as a result, there is no common agreement when it comes to the dimensions of

workplace well-being to be measured (Zanjari & Sani, 2014). It has been acknowledged that it is a multidimensional construct because workplace well-being ranges from physical or health, emotional, psychological, and mental to the social aspect of the workplace (Lomas, 2019, Fleurbaey and Blanchet 2013, Reeves, 2019). Researchers have been trying to figure out the common dimensions to be measured related to workplace well-being. Some researchers have been proposing the hedonic aspect of well-being at work such as measuring the experience of emotion in a work situation (Burke et al. (1989, cited by Czerw, 2019) and the experience of work satisfaction (Neuberger & Allerbeck 1978; Spector 1997 cited by Czerw, 2019). Others also suggested including the meaning of work ((Wrzesniewski et al. 2003), engagement of work (Schaufeli and Bakker 2004), and a sense of the meaning of work (Steger et al. 2012). From these multi-dimensions, the researchers have been finding it difficult to agree on the general model of workplace well-being but there is a need to identify common dimensions of workplace well-being to be measured as suggested by Van Horn et al. (2004) and they proposed two dimensions such as hedonic and eudaimonic dimensions. His recommendations seem to be consistent with the proposal of Biswas-Diener, et.al (2009) and Huta and Waterman (2014), that workplace well-being can be measured from the two dimensions namely hedonic and eudaimonic dimensions. The current researcher is adopting these two dimensions of workplace well-being to measure the workplace well-being of employees of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region, in the Philippines.

Hedonic Workplace well-being: comfortable workplace

Hedonic workplace well-being is related to work experience where employees experience more pleasure than pain. It assumes that by increasing the amount of pleasure and reducing the amount of pain, well-being can be achieved or happy life can be achieved (Vanhoutte & Nazroo, 2014). It is often referred to as subjective well-being because it defines a happy or good life. Those who adopt a hedonic view argue that good life or happy life is only achieved through the maximization of pleasurable experience and eliminating the pains (Kahneman et al., 1999, Diener, 1984). According to Kahneman et al., (1999) hedonic well-being is consisting of a cognitive evaluation of life experience and affective evaluation of life experience. Cognitive evaluation involves the evaluation of life satisfaction in which the individual evaluates or assesses his/her level of satisfaction in his/her life. While the affective dimension of hedonic well-being consists of moods and emotions, both positive and negative emotions (Vanhoutte & Nazroo, 2014). The affective dimension is often time influenced by mental health conditions (Demakakos, McMunn, and Steptoe, 2010). Someone achieves well-being when he/she feels more positive emotions and feels less negative emotions.

Eudaimonic Workplace Well-Being: The realization of basic psychological needs of autonomy, relatedness, and competence.

The eudaimonic approach to well-being is somehow in contradiction with the hedonic approach to well-being. If hedonic well-being sees the attainment of subjective well-being by increasing the amount of pleasurable experience and minimizing pains or negative experience, however, eudaimonic well-being is achieved through the attainment of the meaning of life and the full-realization of the self. It is attained through the full functioning of the person (Ryan and Deci, 2001) and this is related to psychological well-being. Deci and Ryan (2000, cited by Abun, 2019) have identified the three basic psychological needs to be realized to achieve the full potential of a human person and they are autonomy, relatedness, and competence needs. When the three needs are not realized, the growth of a human person is hampered and it leads to frustration (Vansteenkiste & Ryan, 2013, cited by Abun, 2019). Autonomy is achieved

through the exercise of freedom in which the employees are given the freedom to carry out their duties and responsibilities of their own volition. They are the ones to direct their work (Legault, 2016, cited by Abun, 2019). The workplace must provide an environment in which the autonomy needs can flourish (Smith, 2019). Besides autonomy need is a relatedness need. This is the innate desire of human beings to connect to or related to others. Alderfer, as cited by Abun (2019), had already identified three basic human needs and they are existence, relatedness, and growth needs. Relatedness need is a social need in which human beings need to get involved with family, friends, co-workers, and employers. He needs to love and care and to be loved and be cared for (Baumeister & Leary, 1995). This need must be given chance to grow to achieve the full potential of human growth. Lastly is the competence need. This is still considered basic psychological needs and it is an innate desire to feel effective in interacting with the environment (Deci & Ryan, 2000; White, 1959, cited by Abun, 2019). The competence need of employees can only grow when the environment allows them to exercise their capability and skills by giving them a challenging task.

Organizational Citizenship Behavior

Organizational success does not just rely on the financial capital but also relies on the behaviour of its employees. Not all employees behave the same way because some of them show up for work just to get a salary and they do not want to be late for their work because it means a deduction to their salary. Those who show up for work for salary will not lose extra time for doing other things beyond their prescribed duties and responsibilities for the good of the organization. But some employees show up for work, not only for the sake of salary for themselves but the sake of the organization and other employees. They can sacrifice their time beyond office hour to do other things which benefit the organization and other people. This is the behaviour that the management is looking for and this is called organizational citizenship behaviour (OCB). Organizational citizenship behaviour means positive work behaviours that are not confined within the prescribed responsibilities but beyond. In other words, employees are contributing more to the organization beyond their job description (Organ & Ryan, 1995). Recognizing the importance of OCB toward the growth of the organization, many researchers and practitioners have started finding out different dimensions of OCB (Chiun Lo & Ramayah, 2009). The interest in identifying organizational citizenship behaviour was first done by Smith, Organ, and Near (1983) and also Bateman and Organ (1983). They identified two components of organizational citizenship behaviour as altruism and general compliance. They contended that these two behaviours serve to improve organizational effectiveness (Smith, Organ, and Near, 1983, Bateman & Organ (1983, Organ, et.al. 2006). Since then, many researchers have conducted researches and they have found that OCB correlates to the organizational outcome such as service quality ((Bettencourt & Brown, 1997; Bell & Menguc, 2002, cited by Chiun Lo & Ramayah, 2009), organizational commitment ((Podsakoff, McKenzie & Bommer, 1996), and job involvement (Dimitriades, 2007).

Although many studies have been conducted to identify the dimensions of OCB, however, there have been no common agreements when it comes to global dimensions of organizational citizenship behaviours. Organ (1988 cited by Wang, et.al. 2013) proposed five dimensions of organizational citizenship behaviour which include conscientiousness, sportsmanship, civic virtue, courtesy, and altruism. Sportsmanship refers to employees who are not complaining when they encounter little problems in the organization and always maintain a positive view of what is happening around them (Wang, et.al, 2013). Conscientiousness explains employees who are mindful of others or those around him/them and have a sense of duty toward others (Psychologist World, n.d). Civic virtue is referring to the behaviour of

employees who are actively participating in any organizational activities such as meetings that may not be required but important, reading work-related information, discussing work issues outside of official time (Organ, 1988). Courtesy refers to polite and considerate behaviour toward other people or co-workers (Organ, 1988). Altruism is helping behaviours. Employees who have altruistic behaviour are always willing to help other co-workers or clients when they encounter a problem (Organ, 1988). These five dimensions encompass other behaviours such as following company rules, helping the organization, and participating in organizational activities. (Podsakoff, et.al (2000) had also proposed seven dimensions of organizational citizenship behaviour which have been included in the five dimensions presented by Organ (1988) and these include helping behaviours, sportsmanship, organizational loyalty, organizational compliance, individual initiative, civic virtue, and self-development. These five dimensions (Organ, 1988) and seven dimensions (Podsakoff, et.al (2000) are summarized into one dimension by Fox and Specter (n.d) which is altruistic behaviour. The altruistic behaviour covers different dimensions offered by Organ (1988) and Podsakoff, et.al. 2000). Altruistic behaviour refers to the behaviours of employees that help co-workers with related work issues and non-related to work issues (OCBP) and behaviours that help or benefit the organization (OCBO). They are doing this beyond the scope of the job description and voluntarily without expecting rewards.

Source: National Library of Medicine (2020)

Figure 1: the conceptual framework reflects the independent and dependent variables. Independent variables are variables that stand alone and can influence the dependent variables. While dependent variables are variables that can be changed because of the independent variables (National Library of Medicine, 2020)

Statement of the Problems

The study intends to determine the correlation between the workplace well-being of employees and their organizational citizenship behaviour. It specifically answers the following questions:

1. What is the workplace well-being of employees in terms of:
 - a. Hedonic workplace well-being

- b. Eudaimonic workplace well-being in terms of
 1. Autonomy Need
 2. Relatedness Need
 3. Competence need
2. What is the organizational citizenship behaviour of the employees in terms of
 - a. OCBO
 - b. OCBP
3. Is there a relationship between workplace well-being and organizational citizenship behaviour?

Assumption

The study assumes that workplace well-being affects the employees' organizational citizenship behaviours and the two variables can be measured. The study also assumes that the questionnaires are valid and the answers are objectives.

Hypothesis

Studies have found that workplace well-being affects the performance of employees and the performance of the organization (Krekel, et.al, 2019, Haddon, 2018). **The current study hypothesizes that the workplace well-being of employees influences their organizational citizenship behaviour.**

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The coverage of the study is the Divine Word Colleges in Ilocos Region. These two colleges are located in two provinces: Ilocos Sur and Ilocos Norte. The study delimits its investigation on the two dimensions of well-being which are hedonic and eudaimonic well-being and one dimension of organizational citizenship behaviour which is altruistic behaviour. The study is limited because it does not cover all Divine Word Colleges in the Philippines and therefore the result may not represent the picture of all Divine Word Colleges in the Philippines.

Research Methodology

The scientific study should always follow a scientific process of investigation and therefore it follows a certain research methodology. The methodology is the process of how the study is carried out. It deploys certain procedures to identify, select, and analyze the data related to the concerned topic (Wilkinson, 2000, Leedy, 1974). Therefore the current study applies certain methods of investigation such as research design, data gathering instruments method, the population of the study, the locale of the study, data gathering procedures, and the statistical treatment of data.

Research Design of the study

The research design of the study is the descriptive assessment and descriptive correlational research design. Ariola (2006) contended that a descriptive correlation study is intended to describe the relationship among variables without seeking to establish a causal connection. While descriptive research is simply to describe a population, a situation, or a phenomenon. It is also used to describe profiles, frequency distribution, describe characteristics of people, situation, or phenomena. In short, it answers the question of what, when, how, where, and not why question (McCombes, 2020).

The locale of the Study

The locale of the study was Divine Word Colleges namely Divine Word College of Laoag and Divine Word College of Vigan. These two colleges are located in Vigan City, the heritage city of Ilocos Sur, and Laoag City, the capital of Ilocos Norte.

Population

The respondents of the study are the employees of these colleges. Since the number of employees is limited, therefore, the total enumeration sampling or 150 was used and thus all faculty and employees from the two colleges were taken as respondents of the study.

Data Gathering instruments

The study adopted validated questionnaires of Czerw (2019) in a Diagnosing Well-Being in Work Context – Eudemonic Well-Being in the Workplace Questionnaire and of Fox and Ryan and Deci (2000) on eudaimonic workplace well-being. Specter (n.d) from Pennsylvania University and Chiun Lo and Ramayah (2009) on organizational citizenship behaviour (OCB). The questionnaires that are taken from Fox and Specter (n.d) are only those that are related to measuring the acts to help co-workers with job-related and the acts that are helping the organization which is classified as OCBO and OCBP.

Data Gathering Procedures

To preserve the integrity of scientific research, the data were gathered after the approval of the Presidents of different colleges. The researcher sent a letter to the president and after the letters were approved, the questionnaires were distributed by the researcher's representative. Then the researcher's representative from each institution collected the data and submitted it to the researcher for tabulation.

Ethical Procedures

The study was carried out after the research ethics committee examined and approved the content of the paper if it does not violate ethical standards and if it does not cause harm to human life and the environment.

Statistical Treatment of Data

To analyze the data, a descriptive and inferential statistic was used. The weighted mean was used to determine the level of workplace well-being of employees and the Pearson r was used to measure the correlation between workplace well-being and organizational citizenship behaviour of employees.

The following ranges of values with their descriptive interpretation will be used:

<i>Statistical Range</i>	<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>	<i>Overall Descriptive Rating</i>
4.21-5.00	<i>strongly agree</i>	<i>Very High</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Agree</i>	<i>High</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>somewhat agree</i>	<i>Moderate</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Low/High</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Strongly disagree</i>	<i>Very Low/Very High</i>

IV. Empirical Data Presentation and Analysis

Research is considered scientific research when it follows a certain method of investigation and supported by data. Thus this part presents and interprets the data that were

gathered through questionnaires. The presentation follows the structure or the arrangement of the statement of the problems.

Problem 1: What is the workplace well-being of employees in terms of:

- a. Hedonic workplace well-being
- b. Eudemonic workplace well-being in terms of
 - 1. Autonomy Need
 - 2. Relatedness Need
 - 3. Competence need

Table 1. The Workplace Well-being of Employees in terms of Hedonic Workplace Well-being

INDICATORS	Mean	DR
1. Thanks to the institution, the institution provides enough benefits.	3.21	SWA
2. I think that the work I am doing is interesting.	3.66	A
3. The transparency of rules in my company is making my work easier.	3.24	SWA
4. I believe that the position in which I work is adequate to my skills.	3.59	A
5. I seldom encounter problems in my work.	3.35	SWA
6. I feel satisfied with my work.	3.61	A
7. I feel that the atmosphere at my work is welcoming and friendly.	3.61	A
8. My institution is a positive workplace.	3.48	A
9. I believe I am liked and accepted at work.	3.66	A
10. I feel that my supervisors appreciate my work.	3.57	A
Composite Mean	3.50	A

Source: Czerw (2019),

Legend:

- 4.21-5.00 *strongly agree/Very High*
- 3.41-4.20 *Agree/High*
- 2.61-3.40 *somewhat agree/Moderate*
- 1.81-2.60 *Disagree/Low*
- 1.00-1.80 *Strongly disagree/Very Low*

As indicated by the data on the table, it appears that as a whole, the workplace well-being of employees in terms of the hedonic workplace well-being gained a composite mean of 3.50 which is described as "agree or high". These composite means indicates that the hedonic well-being of employees is not very high but high and it is not also moderate, low or very low. Even when the items are taken singly, the majority of the items fall within the same mean range level with the description of "agree or high" such as "the work is interesting (3.66), the position in which I work is adequate to my skills (3.59), feeling satisfied with my work (3.61), the atmosphere at my work is welcoming and friendly (3.61), the institution is a positive workplace (3.48), I am liked and accepted at work (3.66), and my supervisors appreciate my work (3.57). Three items fall within the same mean ranges which is described as "somewhat agree or moderate" such as "the institution provides enough benefits (3.21), the transparency of rules in my company is making my work easier (3.24), and I seldom encounter problems in my work" (3.35).

The composite mean of 3.50 suggests that as a whole, the employees agree that they feel highly comfortable working at the Divine Word Colleges. The environment is highly comfortable but not very highly comfortable. However, there are several aspects needed to be improved such as benefits, transparency and other related problems that affect the work of employees.

Table 2. The Workplace Well-being of Employees in terms of Eudemonic Workplace Well-being

INDICATORS	Mean	DR
<i>Autonomy Needs</i>		
1. At work, I feel a sense of choice and freedom in the things I undertake.	3.44	A
2. I feel that my decisions on my job reflect what I want.	3.53	A
3. I feel my choices on my job express who really, I am.	3.48	A
4. I feel I have been doing what interests me in my job.	3.58	A
Composite Mean	3.51	A
<i>Relatedness Need</i>		
1. I feel that the people I care at work about also care about me.	3.66	A
2. I feel connected with people who care for me at work and for whom I care at work.	3.74	A
3. At work, I feel close and connected with other people who are important to me.	3.74	A
4. I experience a warm feeling with the people I spend time with at work.	3.72	A
Composite Mean	3.72	A
<i>Competence Need</i>		
1. I feel confident that I can do things well on my job.	3.79	A
2. At work, I feel capable of what I do.	3.81	A
3. When I am at work, I feel competent to achieve my goals.	3.85	A
4. In my job, I feel I can complete a difficult task.	3.83	A
Composite Mean	3.82	A
Composite Mean	3.68	A

Source: Fox and Ryan and Deci, (2000)

Legend:

4.21-5.00	<i>strongly agree/Very High</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Agree/High</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>somewhat agree/Moderate</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Disagree/Low</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Strongly disagree/Very Low</i>

Based on the data as projected on the table, it reveals that as a whole, eudemonic workplace well-being of employees obtained a composite mean rating of 3.68 which is described as "agree or high". This rating indicates that the eudemonic well-being of employees is not very high but high and it is not also moderate, low or very low. Even if the components of eudemonic well-being are taken singly, all the three components are rated within

the same mean ranges with the same description of "agree or high" such as autonomy need (3.51), relatedness need (3.72) and competence need (3.82). This result suggests that all employees agree on the extent of the realization of their basic psychological needs. In terms of autonomy, they agree the extent of the realization of their autonomy needs such as "they feel a sense of choice and freedom in the things they undertake (3.44), the decisions on their job reflect what they want (3.53), their choices on their job express who really they are (3.48), and they feel they have been doing what interests them in their job" (3.58). Along with relatedness need, they employee also agree the extent of the realization of their relatedness needs such as "feeling that the people they care at work about also care about them (3.66), feeling connected with people who care for them at work and for whom they care at work (3.74), feeling close and connected with other people who are important to them (3.74), and experiencing a warm feeling with the people they spend time with at work" (3.72). Lastly concerning the realization of their competence need, all employee agree the extent of the realization of their competence needs such as "I feeling confident that they can do things well on their job (3.79), feeling capable at what they do (3.81), feeling competent to achieve their goals (3.85) and feeling that they can complete difficult task" (3.83).

Table 3. Summary of Workplace Well-being of Employees

ITEMS	Mean	DR
I. Hedonic Workplace Well-being	3.50	A
II. Eudemonic Workplace Well-being	3.68	A
Overall Mean	3.59	A

As shown on the summary table, it demonstrates that as a whole, the workplace well-being of the Divine Word Colleges' employees in the Ilocos Region garnered an overall mean rating of 3.59 which is described as "agree or high". This indicates that the workplace well-being of the Divine Word Colleges is not very high but high and it is not also moderate, low or very low. Even when taking them separately, both dimensions got the same level of mean rating in which all employees agree on the extent of the realization of their hedonic and eudemonic well-being with the mean rating of 3.50 and 3.68. This result signifies that all employees agree on the extent of the realization of their comfortable workplace and the extent of the realization of their basic psychological needs.

Problem 2: What is the organizational citizenship behaviour of the employees in terms of

- a. OCBO
- b. OCBP

Table 4. The Organizational Citizenship Behaviour of the Employees of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region in terms of OCBO

INDICATORS	Mean	DR
1. Help new employees get oriented to the job.	3.67	A
2. Offered suggestions to improve how work is done.	3.65	A
3. Volunteered for extra work assignments.	3.60	A

4. Said good things about your employer in front of others.	3.64	A
5. Said good things about your school in the community outside the school.	3.65	A
6. Give up meals and other breaks to complete the work.	3.59	A
7. Offered suggestions for improving the work environment.	3.66	A
8. came in early or stay late without pay to complete a project or task.	3.71	A
9. Volunteer to share new job knowledge or skills with other employees.	3.63	A
Composite Mean	3.64	A

Source: Specter (n.d)

Legend:

4.21-5.00	<i>strongly agree/Very High</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Agree/High</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>somewhat agree/Moderate</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Disagree/Low</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Strongly disagree/Very Low</i>

Based on the data, it displays that as a whole, the organizational citizenship behaviour of employees in terms of OCBO (organizational citizenship behaviour that directs toward helping the organization) obtained a composite mean of 3.64 which is interpreted as “agree or high”. This composite mean rating points out that organizational citizenship behaviour of the employees in terms of OCBO is not very high but high and it is not also moderate, low or very low. Even when the items are taken singly, all items fall within the same level of mean rating with the same description such as “helping new employees get oriented to the job (3.67), offering suggestions to improve how work is done (3.65), volunteering for extra work assignments (3.60), saying good things about their employer in front of others (3.64), saying good things about their school in the community outside the school (3.65), giving up meals and other breaks to complete the work (3.59), offering suggestions for improving the work environment (3.66), coming in early or stay late without pay to complete a project or task (3.71), and volunteering to share new job knowledge or skills with other employees" (3.63). These results suggest that all employees highly agree that they are helping the institution in one way or another.

Table 5. The Organizational Citizenship Behavior of the Employees of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region in terms of OCBP

INDICATORS	Mean	DR
1. Lent a compassionate ear when someone had a work problem.	3.72	A
2. Lent a compassionate ear when someone had a personal problem.	3.75	A
3. Change vacation schedule, workdays, or shifts to accommodate co-workers' needs.	3.67	A
4. Help a less capable co-worker lift a heavy box or other objects.	3.77	A

5. Went out of the way to give co-worker encouragement or express appreciation.	3.73	A
6. Defended co-worker who was being ‘put down’ or spoken ill by other co-workers or supervisors.	3.69	A
7. Help co-workers with personal matters such as sharing food or drinks.	3.77	A
8. Lent money or personal property to a co-worker.	3.67	A
Composite Mean	3.72	A

Source: Specter (n.d)

Legend:

4.21-5.00	<i>strongly agree/Very High</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Agree/High</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>somewhat agree/Moderate</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Disagree/Low</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Strongly disagree/Very Low</i>

As projected by the data on the table, it exhibits that as a whole, the organizational citizenship behaviour of employees in terms of OCBP (organizational citizenship behaviours that direct toward helping personal problems of other employees or co-workers) obtained a composite mean of 3.72 which is described as “agree or high”. This output suggests that the organizational citizenship behaviours of employees along with the OCBP is not very high but high and it is also not moderate, low or very low. Even when the items are taken separately, they all fall within the same level of mean rating with the description of “agree or high” such as “lending a compassionate ear when someone had a work problem (3.72), lending a compassionate ear when someone had a personal problem (3.75), changing vacation schedule, workdays, or shifts to accommodate co-workers' needs(3.67), helping a less capable co-worker lift a heavy box or other objects (3.77), going out of the way to give co-worker encouragement or express appreciation (3.73), defending co-worker who was being ‘put down’ or spoken ill by other co-workers or supervisors (3.69), helping co-workers with personal matters such as sharing food or drinks (3.77) and lending money or personal property to a co-worker" (3.67). These results imply that all employees highly agree that they are helping their co-workers who have personal problems that may affect their work.

Table 6. Summary of Organizational Citizenship Behaviour of the Employees

ITEMS	Mean	DR
I. OCBO: Acts that direct toward the organization	3.64	A
II. OCBP: Acts that are directed toward a person	3.72	A
Overall Mean	3.68	A

As indicated by the data on the summary table, it shows that as a whole, the organizational citizenship behaviour of the employees in terms OCBO and OCBP receives an overall mean rating of 3.68 which is described as “agree or high”. It just suggests that overall the organizational citizenship behaviours of the employees are high which means that they highly help the organization and the other employees when others have personal problem. Even when the dimensions are taken separately, they all show that their OCBP and OCBO are also high with the mean rating of 3.64 and 3.72.

Problem 3: Is there a relationship between workplace well-being and organizational citizenship behaviour?

Table 9. Relationship between Work Environment and Work Engagement

		OCBO	OCBP
Hedonic Workplace Well-being	Pearson Correlation	.036	-.005
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.661	.953
	N	150	150
Eudemonic Workplace Well-being under Autonomy	Pearson Correlation	.097	.038
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.239	.641
	N	150	150
Eudemonic Workplace Well-being under relatedness	Pearson Correlation	-.098	-.063
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.235	.444
	N	150	150
Eudemonic Workplace Well-being under the competence	Pearson Correlation	.012	.010
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.881	.908
	N	150	150

Source: SPSS

Based on the data presented in the table demonstrates that as a whole, there is no significant relationship between workplace well-being and organizational citizenship behaviour. Even if the different dimensions of workplace well-being and organizational citizenship behaviours are taken separately, the data reveals that there is no correlation between those dimensions. It suggests that organizational citizenship behaviours of the employees are not affected by the workplace well-being but by other factors that are not included in the current study. It means that organizational citizenship behaviour of the employees has nothing to do with workplace well-being.

Result and Discussion

Based on the finding of the current study, it shows that there is no correlation between workplace well-being and organizational citizenship behaviour of the employees. This finding contributes to the complex discussion on the role of workplace well-being to affect the organizational citizenship behaviour of the employees because this result does not seem to be aligned with the previous studies. This result contradicts the finding of Zu, et.al. (2019) that workplace well-being affects positively the organizational citizenship behaviour of the employees. This finding is also supported by the previous research of Mukherjee (2017) about the positive effect of workplace well-being on organizational citizenship behaviour. Even the study of Palihakkara and Weerakkody (2019) on the impact of employee's happiness on the organizational citizenship behaviour of the employees contradicts the current finding.

The contradictory finding of the recent study from the previous studies can be caused by several factors. First is the dimensions of the workplace well-being and the organizational citizenship behaviours that are being investigated or measured are not always the same. Second is the context where the study is carried out is different. This implies that the same study can have a different result if the studies are conducted in a different environment. There can be intervening factors that mediate the effect of workplace well-being on organizational citizenship behaviour. Therefore, there is no conclusive agreement on the positive or negative effect of workplace well-being on the organizational citizenship behaviours of employees. The current

study suggests that organizational citizenship behaviours of the employees do not necessarily depend on the hedonic and eudemonic well-being.

Conclusion

The purpose of the study is to determine the effect of workplace well-being on the organizational citizenship behaviours of the employees which are directed toward the individual and the organization. The study is supported by the theories on workplace well-being and organizational citizenship behaviour and carried out following the scientific methodologies with descriptive assessment and correlational research design. Questionnaires were used to gather the data and weighted mean and Pearson r correlation was used to analyse the data. The study found that the workplace well-being of employees such as hedonic and eudemonic well-being and the organizational citizenship behaviour of the employees are considered high. Based on the Pearson r correlation analysis found that there is no correlation between workplace well-being and the organizational citizenship behaviour of the employees. Therefore the hypothesis of the study that there is a correlation between workplace well-being and organizational citizenship behaviours are rejected.

This finding contributes to a wider discussion on the role of workplace well-being on the organizational citizenship behaviours of the employees. The result implies that there is no conclusive answer to the role of workplace well-being on organizational citizenship. Other organizational factors must be studied and included in the study of workplace well-being and organizational citizenship behaviours.

The current study recognizes its limitation particularly on the scope of the study. The coverage of the study is limited to the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region which may not represent the whole Divine Word Colleges. Further, the population of the study is also considered limited because it covered only the employees of the colleges being investigated. It is important to conduct another study to include other colleges and more population.

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